

Building of a Corporate Governance System in Jordan: A Critique of the Current Framework

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Abstract

Corporate governance is developing rapidly in many countries across the world. In this article, the existing state of corporate governance in Jordan is examined. Jordan does not have a corporate governance code *per se*. The article reveals that overall Jordan has in place some of the features of corporate governance best practice, but that there remains further progress to be made in areas such as independence of directors, compensation, preemptive rights for shareholders, correlation between shareholding and entitlement to seats on the board, and the role of stakeholders. The article recommends legal reforms, principally through amendments to the Companies Law of 1997, in order to enhance corporate governance in Jordan.

Key Words: corporate governance, Jordan, Companies Law, Reform.

I. Introduction

The generally accepted definition of the phrase “corporate governance” comes from the seminal Report of the Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance (the Cadbury Report).¹ The Cadbury Report defines corporate governance as the system by which companies are directed and controlled.² In other words, corporate governance is

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¹ The Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance was chaired by Sir Adrian Cadbury. The Cadbury Committee may be considered the mother of all corporate governance committees. The Cadbury Committee reported on corporate governance practices, primarily on the control and reporting functions of boards and the role of auditors. See Report of the Committee on the Financial Aspects of Corporate Governance (Dec. 1, 1992), available at <www.worldbank.org/html/fpd/privatesector/cg/docs/cadbury.pdf> (last visited March 1, 2006).

² *Id.* at. 2.5

about the governance of corporations. At its most basic, corporate governance deals with the relationships among the board, management and investors with respect to the control of corporations.

The development of corporate governance standards was influenced and fostered by globalization.³ Globalization has had a long history of affecting the development of the corporation. For example, the development of chartered companies in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries arose out of increased trade.⁴

Corporate governance issues can be viewed as a trade-like issue. Trade increases competition, which has the effect of breaking down local barriers resulting in increased competition in the products market. Open competition directly affects the performance of a country's firms, raising the issue of whether a particular corporate governance model is a factor in a firm's performance. In addition, competition for capital means that corporations seeking capital need to provide good governance practices.⁵ Indeed, investors demand good governance practices as a condition of investment.⁶ Therefore, higher corporate governance standards in Jordan may provide a means of enhancing its competitiveness.

³ Globalization involves a stretching of economic activities across regions and marked by the intensification of interconnectedness and flows of trade, investment, finance, migration, culture. Moreover, globalization is speeding up global interactions and processes as the development of world-wide systems of transport and communication increases the velocity of the diffusion of ideas, goods, information, capital and people. See David Held & Anthony McGrew, *Globalization*, Oxford Companion to Politics of the World 324 (Joel Krieger ed., 2001).

⁴ See John Micklethwait & Adrian Wooldridge, *The Company: A Short History of a Revolutionary Idea* 17-24 (2003).

⁵ See generally Amir N. Licht, *Cross-Listing and Corporate Governance: Bonding or Avoiding?* 4 Chi. J. Int'l L. 141 (2003).

⁶ See *Governing the Modern Corporation*, *The Economist*, May 5, 2001, at S30.

While the U.S. had its headline-grabbing corporate scandals involving companies such as Enron and World Com,⁷ Jordan also experienced its share of corporate troubles affecting not only large entities such as Petra Bank,⁸ but also some smaller companies.⁹ Over the years, there have been charges that companies hide information, have poor internal controls, and have negligent and incompetent boards of directors. In some instances there have been claims of fraud on the part of directors and auditors.¹⁰ All of which have underscored the need for higher corporate governance standards.

This article will examine Jordan's current position on corporate governance of publicly-traded companies. The article will comment on the role of the board of directors, conflicts of interest and related party transactions, liability of directors. Moreover, this article will discuss the role of the audit committee and auditors, and disclosure and transparency. This article concludes with comments on the current status of corporate governance in Jordan and provides suggestions that might be considered as Jordan considers amendments to Companies Law or implementing regulations in order to improve corporate governance further.

⁷ See William J. Carney, *The Costs of being Public after the Sarbanes-Oxley: The Irony of "Going Private"*, 55 *Emory L.J.* 141 (2006).

⁸ Petra Bank was Jordan's second bank. Due to poor corporate governance, Petra Bank collapsed and became one of the biggest corporate scandals in Jordan's history. See *A Delicate State of Affairs*, *The Economist* (Oct. 4, 2003). Another scandal involved IT company and the secret police where \$1 billion in loans went astray. This scandal became Jordan's largest scandals. See *The Fall of a Kingmaker*, *The Economist* (July 19, 2003).

⁹ See M. Al-Basheer, *The Non-Seriousness of the Regulatory Authorities Prevented Stopping Corruption and Failure of Companies*, *Al-Rai Newspaper* (Apr. 21, 2001).

¹⁰ Telephone Interview with a lawyer linked to corporate fraud cases in Jordan who asked for anonymity (August 21, 2006).

II. Background

The origins of Jordan company law can be traced back to approximately 1929. The Jordanian Company Law of 1929 was modeled after British companies acts. After World War II, French influence on Jordanian corporate law displaced the British influence.¹¹

In the 1950s, partnerships were the dominant form of commercial enterprise. In 1964, with the promulgation of the Companies Law, a legal mechanism existed for the creation and operation of joint ventures, public shareholding companies, and limited liability companies. Twenty-five years after the Companies Law was promulgated a new law was enacted in 1989. The Companies Law of 1989 added new provisions related to formation, management, and liquidation of companies. The Companies Law of 1989 was further amended in 1997. The current Companies Law of 1997 includes provisions related to consolidation and foreign companies operating in Jordan.¹²

Following the establishment of the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) in 1999, the government of Jordan encouraged local companies to expand and issue securities to the public. A large number of companies are family-owned with some public float or otherwise closely-held with a small minimum investor float.¹³ The owners of these companies had been reluctant to take their companies public for fear of diluting the controlling family's stake. The Companies Law offered protections to their ownership rights. A company could go public and be listed on the ASE while the founding

¹¹ See Thabet Koraytem, *The Islamic Nature of the Saudi Regulations for Companies*, 15.1 Arab L. Quarterly 63, 64 (2000).

¹² See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), as amended by Provisional Companies Law No. 40 of 2002, Official Gazette No. 4533 (Feb. 17, 2002).

¹³ See Jill Solomon & Aris Solomon, *Corporate Governance and Accountability* 173 (West Sussex, England: John Wiley & Sons Ltd 2005) (Jordan's system of corporate governance is insider-oriented with most companies being owned predominantly by founding families).

shareholders maintained sixty percent of the shares.¹⁴ These policies provided incentives for the dispersal of corporate ownership, thus encouraging current controllers to maintain control at lower levels of ownership concentration.¹⁵

The publicly held corporations now play important role in the Jordanian economy. Publicly held corporations can be viewed in purely economic terms as a means by which capital is raised from a large number of public savers and used by businesses. There are publicly traded corporations in which there is a control group. They range from traditional family owned businesses like the major banks (Arab Bank) to industrial companies (Kawther Investment and International Textile Manufacturing) where control remains in the original owners. The government of Jordan owned some companies. Institutional investors do not have great influence. However, the Social Security Corporation (pension fund) and Jordan Investment Corporation, in particular, hold a large percentage of shareholding.

There are 200 companies, dominated by banks and insurance companies, listed on ASE.¹⁶ In 2005, market capitalization rose to a high of just over \$14.2 billion tempting new investors to enter the market to take advantage of the riches to be acquired through share ownership.¹⁷ In 2006 the market dropped precipitously and while stabilized, it has yet to regain its former highs.¹⁸ Some companies declared bankruptcy and were de-listed from ASE. There are many factors that contributed to the troubles in the capital market.

These factors include easy credit for investors and questionable practices of company

¹⁴ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 99.

¹⁵ Most of the world has concentrated ownership while the U.S. and UK have a widely dispersed ownership structure. The widely dispersed ownership structure usually relies more on market financing while the concentrated ownership structure looks more to private financing. See Rafael La Porta et al., *Corporate Ownership around the World*, 54 J. Fin. 471, 511-13 (1999).

¹⁶ See Amman Exchange, Vol. XXV.1 Banks in Jordan Magazine 74 (Jan. 2006).

¹⁷ See Amman Stock Exchange, Monthly Statistical Bulletin 36 (Sep. 2006).

¹⁸ See Amman Stock Exchange, Jordan Times (June 4, 2006).

founders. A stronger system of corporate governance likely would have protected the market from some of the troubles. The Companies Law should be rewritten to assure adequate internal controls, provide greater protection for all stakeholders of a company, emphasizes the vital importance of the role of auditors, and promote independence of the board of directors and clarify its responsibilities.

II. Rights of Shareholders

Registration in the company's shareholder registry constitutes proof of ownership. The Companies Law of 1997 provides a secure method of ownership registration. Companies must maintain their own share registers where the shareholding of investors is recorded.¹⁹ Shareholders are free to transfer shares.²⁰ In case of transfer of shares, the purchaser or, as the case may be, the seller can require amendment of the register to record the change in shares' ownership.²¹

Any shareholder can have access to the company share register for any "reasonable cause" and have a copy of the register for a reasonable fee.²² However, in practice, companies do not provide access to their share registers. A shareholder of a company should be entitled to inspect company share records if the inspection is for a proper purpose that is reasonably related to such person's interest as a stockholder. Therefore, on the question of gaining access to the company's register, the focus should be on shareholder's purpose. For example, a shareholder should be entitled to access company

¹⁹ The Securities Depository Center, which acts as a de facto central registry, also has the responsibility for shareholder record-keeping. Companies share registers mirror the registers maintained by the Securities Depository Center. See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 98.

²⁰ The Companies Law of 1997, however, requires the lapse of two years before shares of founders can be transferred. *Id.* art. 100.

²¹ *Id.* art. 98.a.

²² *Id.* art. 98.d.

share register to evaluate the value of the shares before being acquired by another company.

The Companies Law of 1997 gives a shareholder certain powers. For example, shareholders are given the right to obtain and approve the company's audited annual report.²³ Moreover, shareholders have the right to elect members of the board of directors.²⁴ However, the Companies Law of 1997 does not provide for cumulative voting which could enhance the ability of minor shareholders to elect at least one director.²⁵ Government and corporate shareholders must have representatives, who are appointed but not elected, in the board of directors proportional to ownership.²⁶ Dismissing members of the board who are appointed by the government is difficult as they cannot be removed by the shareholders general meeting.²⁷ All directors should be elected by secret ballot. The Companies Law of 1997 should not differentiate between natural and juristic persons regarding selecting members of the board.

The Companies Law of 1997 requires that shareholders be notified of and have the power to vote in respect of corporate changes such as amendments to the company charter, merger or reorganization of the company, and winding up or voluntary

²³ *Id.* art. 171. In practice, a summary of the annual report is published in two newspapers. In addition, while the Companies Law of 1997 requires auditing of semi-annual reports, these reports are merely reviewed by an auditor. Material facts are disclosed upon occurrence.

²⁴ Directors are elected by a secret ballot. *Id.* art. 132.a & 171.a.

²⁵ Cumulative voting is a system for electing corporate directors whereby a shareholder may multiply his number of shares by the number of open directorship and cast the total for a single candidate. For example, suppose that a public shareholding company has two shareholders, one holding 70 percent of the votes and another holding 30 percent. Five directors need to be elected. If there is not cumulative rule in place, each shareholder will have to vote separately for each director. The majority shareholder will get all five seats because he outvotes the minority shareholder each time by 70:30. If there is cumulative voting, the minority shareholder can take all his votes (five times 20 percent) and cast them for one board member. In this case, the minority shareholder can win a seat. See Robert W. Hamilton & Jonathan R. Macey, *Cases and Materials on Corporations* 534 (8th ed. 2003).

²⁶ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 135.a.

²⁷ *Id.* art. 165.

liquidation of the company.²⁸ The Companies Law of 1997 does not provide that existing shareholders have pre-emption rights to subscribe for newly issued shares in proportion to their relevant shareholding.²⁹ The elimination of preemptive rights significantly impairs the rights of minority shareholders by leaving them without economic protection and active participation in the business.

A shareholder meeting is held annually, within a specified time frame (e.g., 4 months) of the end of the company's fiscal year.³⁰ The annual shareholders' meeting is called by the chairman of the board of directors.³¹ The Companies Law of 1997 requires that the company notifies the shareholders of the agenda for a shareholders' meeting 14 calendar days, a relatively short period of time, in advance of the scheduled shareholders' meeting.³² The notice includes the date, location and agenda of general meetings, as well as full information regarding the issues to be decided at the meeting.³³

Without prior notice, shareholders whose aggregate shareholding represents at least ten percent of the company's issued and outstanding shares can request additional items to be added to the agenda.³⁴ It is preferable if shareholders can add items to agenda before the meeting so that other shareholders would have the time to examine these

²⁸ Decisions on these matters are made by the general assembly in its extraordinary meeting. Decisions are issued by a supermajority of 75 percent of the total shares represented in the meeting. *Id.* art. 175.a & b.

²⁹ Preemptive right is considered a shareholder's privilege to purchase newly issued shares before the shares are offered to the public in an amount proportionate to the shareholder's current holdings in order to prevent dilution of the shareholder's ownership interest. See James D. Cox et al., *Corporations* 16.14, at 475 (1997).

³⁰ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 169.

³¹ The shareholders do not have an explicit power to call for an ordinary general assembly meeting when the board of directors fails to do so.

³² The meeting notice should be extended from 14 days to at least 20 days so as to give opportunity to shareholders to review the meeting materials and prepare for it. Moreover, public shareholding companies could display their annual meeting materials on their World Wide Web sites in time to suppress the mailing of those materials.

³³ The date and time of the meeting should be published in two local newspapers and announced on radio or television. *Id.* art. 144 & 145.

³⁴ *Id.* art. 171.a (9).

items. In the shareholders meeting, shareholders are permitted to ask questions and to obtain replies from management and board members at such shareholders' meeting. Shareholders have the right to vote whether in person or by proxy, that is, to instruct another individual to cast his or her votes on particular resolutions.³⁵ However, postal and Internet voting, whereby investors could vote online, are not permitted. Postal and Internet voting should play greater role.

Although the Companies Law of 1997 does not recognize derivative suits or class actions, shareholders have other vehicles to remedy any violation of their rights.³⁶ For example, in the case of acquisition, shareholders have direct action against directors, general managers, and auditors.³⁷ Moreover, the shareholders can seek redress through the Controller who has wide intervention powers that include removing directors.³⁸ However, the intervention powers of the Controller do not include imposing fines which can be imposed only by courts. The Controller can bring cases against companies, which does not happen in practice. Courts in Jordan are slow and lack extensive expertise in corporate law.³⁹ The higher barriers to bringing a successful suit could explain the lower number of cases brought by the Controller. Changes to the Companies Law of 1997 could

³⁵ A shareholder can give the proxy to another shareholder or a notarized power of attorney to any third party. Proxies are company-specific. For example, the proxy must be in writing, on a special form prepared by the board of directors, approved by the controller, deposited at the company headquarters, and must be examined by the controller. *Id.* art. 179.a.

³⁶ Derivative suits have been considered as the most important procedure the law has yet developed to police the internal affairs of corporations. Class actions seek relief that would provide additional consideration to each shareholder in a way that makes the suit a class of individual claims. By contrast, derivative claims produce recoveries to the corporation. See Robert B. Thompson & Randall S. Thomas, *The Public and Private Faces of Derivative Lawsuits*, 57 *Vand. L. Rev.* 1747, 1756, 1758 (2004) (a derivative suit is brought in the name of the collective entity, the corporation, by an individual shareholder against third party, usually a corporate officers, because of the corporation's failure to take some action against third party).

³⁷ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 234 & 237.

³⁸ For example, in 2005, the Controller received 16 requests to remove members of the board of directors.

³⁹ An average case can last up to five years.

relax any procedural barriers that stand in shareholders way and thus permit the growth of court actions. For example, article 284 of the Companies Law of 1997 was enacted for the specific purpose of ensuring company cases would enjoy expeditious status. In short, shareholders of Jordanian companies have two types of remedies: direct suits and private contractual remedies well-crafted contractual agreements.

III. Inside Trading and Self-dealing

The Companies Law of 1997 prevents and punishes insider trading.⁴⁰ The chairmen of the board of directors, any member of the board of directors, general manager, and employees are prohibited from trading on the basis of insider information or to reveal it to others with the aim of manipulating the price.⁴¹ Any transaction based on insider information is considered void and the insider is liable for fines and damages.⁴²

The Jordan Securities Commission (JSC) plays an important role in monitoring insider trading activities. The JSC monitors insider transaction electronically by matching transactions with its database of insiders. In 2004, the JSC discovered one violation of inside trading rules.⁴³ However, the reaction to insider trading has not been as strong. Though insider trading has been considered a punishable criminal offense, prosecutions and punishments have occurred rarely, if ever. In fact, thus far, Jordan did not impose a penalty of imprisonment for such an offense. In Jordan, corporate insiders should face

⁴⁰ Insiders are those directors, officers and controlling shareholders who trade in their corporation's securities with an informational advantage secured through fiduciary relations with that particular corporation. See Ray J. Grzebielski, Friends, Family, Fiduciaries: Personal Relationships as a Basis for Insider Trading Violations, 51 Cath. U.L. Rev. 467, 476 (2002).

⁴¹ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 166.

⁴² *Id.*

⁴³ In 2003, JSC found twenty-three violations of insider trading rules. See Jordan Securities Commission, Annual Report for 2004, table 3, available at <<http://www.jsc.gov.jo/report/AnnualReport2004.pdf>>. See also Jordan Securities Commission, Annual Report for 2003, table 1, available at <<http://www.jsc.gov.jo/report/AnnualReport2003.pdf>>.

hefty fines and prison sentences for trading securities on the basis of inside information because such practices take unfair advantage of stockholders.

Related-party transactions such as transaction between directors, general manager, and the company are prohibited.⁴⁴ For example, loans made to directors are prohibited. The law requires disclosure by the company of loans made to related parties e.g. parent companies, subsidiaries, directors, employees, or the company or related companies.⁴⁵

However, the definition of related-party transaction is unclear.⁴⁶ Indeed, family members of directors are excluded from prohibition of related-party transaction. Moreover, related-party transactions should not be prohibited by law. Rather, the law should require adequate disclosure and approval processes. For example, the law could require that related-party transactions be approved by an issuer's audit committee or comparable body.

IV. Role of Stakeholders in Corporate Governance in Jordan

The Companies Law of 1997 contains few provisions for protecting the rights of employees, suppliers, and creditors as stakeholders.⁴⁷ In case of bankruptcy proceedings, employees have priority over creditors.⁴⁸ Creditors can object to reduction in capital.⁴⁹ The Companies Law of 1997 permits employee investment and employee stock ownership plans.⁵⁰ However, the use of stock ownership plans is limited because

⁴⁴ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 148.

⁴⁵ *Id.* art. 139.

⁴⁶ Related party could be defined as one that can exercise control or significant influence over another party to the extent that one of the parties may be prevented from pursuing its own separate interests.

⁴⁷ Stakeholders are people whose financial well-being is tied to the corporation's success. Stakeholder groups include employees, consumers, creditors, suppliers, communities, and consumer advocacy representatives, among others. See John C. Carter, *The Rights of Other Corporate Constituencies*, 22 Mem. St. U. L. Rev. 491, 504 (1992).

⁴⁸ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 256.

⁴⁹ *Id.* art. 115.

⁵⁰ *Id.* art. 95.e.

employees prefer cash pay. No effective mechanisms exist for employees to seek redress in case of violation of their rights. Stakeholders have no right to access information. In addition, the law does not permit stakeholder participation in decisions by employee representation on boards. Unlike the German and Japanese systems of corporate governance, employees of the company in Jordan are not given direct role in corporate governance.⁵¹

According to the Companies Law of 1997, board of directors has an obligation to maximize shareholder wealth.⁵² However, doing so could often come at stakeholders' expense. The Companies Law of 1997 should be modified to include the interests of stakeholders because companies are more than just investment vehicles for owners of financial capital. The law must make it explicit that directors are able to consider stakeholder interests without obligating them to act contrary to shareholders' interests. Until the law is modified, directors will be unsure whether they are legally permitted to consider stakeholders' interests because their duties require them to act in accordance with shareholders' interests.

⁵¹ The German Codetermination Act of 1976 requires all stock corporations, *Actiengesellschaft* (AG), over a certain employee base, to have a two-tiered board structure that includes significant employee representation on the supervisory *Aufsichtsrat* board. Codetermination appears to be a model of corporate governance that protects stakeholders because the interests of labor are well represented and well protected. In Japan, labor significantly is involved in corporate decision making through life-time employment. See Mark J. Loewenstein, *What can we Learn from Foreign Systems? Stakeholder Protection in Germany and Japan*, 76 *Tul. L. Rev.* 1673, 1677, 1682, 1686 (2002).

⁵² The requirement that corporate leaders manage a corporation for the exclusive benefit of its shareholders is known within company law as the "shareholder primacy norm." See generally D. Gordon Smith, *The Shareholder Primacy Norm*, 23 *J. Corp. L.* 277 (1998).

V. Financial Disclosure

Disclosure can play an important role in corporate governance.⁵³ This disclosure is necessary to protect investors from making poor trading decisions as a result of being uninformed. Disclosure can assist shareholders in effectively exercising their voting rights.⁵⁴ It can also influence corporate governance by helping shareholders enforce management's fiduciary duties.

Like other countries, the Companies Law of 1997 requires ongoing disclosure. Nevertheless, a detailed comparison of U.S. disclosure requirements for companies that issue securities reveals that the U.S. requires significantly more information.⁵⁵ Differences in the requirements include the amount of detail about the nature of the company's business; data concerning the results of the different lines of business in which the issuer participates; discussion of trends that are identified by management and may affect the company's future liquidity, capital needs, or operating results; and information about management compensation and share ownership. Jordan, in general, puts much less emphasis on full disclosure.

In Jordan, a company is required by law to prepare annual audited financial statements, quarterly financial reports, and group accounts on consolidated basis.⁵⁶ Audited consolidated annual reports are presented to the Controller 21 days prior to general assembly meeting. Annual audited accounts include discussion of activities and

⁵³ Disclosure means any legal obligation that requires a company's management to provide, on a regular basis, information that it otherwise might not be inclined to provide. See Merritt B. Fox, Challenges to Corporate Governance: Required Disclosure and Corporate Governance, 62 *Law & Contemp. Prob.* 113, 114 (1999).

⁵⁴ *Id.* 127.

⁵⁵ See Kerry Shannon Burke, Regulating Corporate Governance through the Market: Comparing the Approaches of the United States, Canada and the United Kingdom, 27 *Iowa J. Corp. L.* 341, 350, 358 (2002).

⁵⁶ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 140.

plans for the following year, balance sheet, profit and loss account, and cash flow statements.⁵⁷ Consolidated semi-annual accounts are presented to the Controller within sixty-days of mid-year.⁵⁸

A company required by law to disclose information on the compensation of board members and key executives. A report containing compensation and benefits of company directors, list of directors, and duration of board membership must be placed at the company headquarters for inspection three days prior to the general assembly meeting.⁵⁹ However, in practice, companies in Jordan disclose the aggregate compensation for members of the board of directors. Aggregate figures are far less revealing. With segmented figures, it is much easier for a shareholder to detect each of director's compensation as there is a breakdown of compensation into separate lines.

Directors are liable for the disclosure of reports.⁶⁰ When directors have the legal obligation and liability to disclose certain information, they may have to gather and analyze information they would otherwise ignore.

The Companies Law of 1997 requires disclosure to users of financial information and market participants information on reasonably foreseeable material risks.⁶¹ These risks include financial market risk such as interest rate or currency risk, dependence on commodities, and risk related to derivatives.

There are several disclosure gaps in the Companies Law of 1997. For example, the Companies Law of 1997 does not require disclosing the employment history of individual

⁵⁷ *Id.*

⁵⁸ *Id.* art. 142.

⁵⁹ *Id.* art. 143.

⁶⁰ The liability is clear since the Companies Law of 1997 states that the directors "shall" place the report at the company headquarters. *Id.*

⁶¹ See Directive of Jordan Securities Commission on Disclosure, Accounting, and Auditing Standards of Issuing Companies of 2004, art. 6.b (10).

board members and key executives. There is no requirement to disclose key issues relevant to employees and stakeholders that may materially affect the performance of the company such as management/employee relations and relations with creditors suppliers and local communities. Moreover, a company is not required to disclose, in its annual report or a similar document, its corporate governance structures and policies such as providing information on the division of authority between shareholders, management, and board members.

JSC is the entity responsible for enforcement of disclosure requirements. The JSC ensures the quality of financial statements and reports. However, the staff responsible for enforcing the disclosure regulations is very small.⁶² Therefore, JSC does not extensively review the quality of disclosures. The JSC should continue to build its capacity to review the quality of disclosures. In general, companies comply with the disclosure requirements and deadlines. However, for some companies meeting disclosure deadlines is an issue.

VI. The Role of Auditors

It is widely acknowledged that auditors play an important role in corporate governance. Auditors are supposed to protect their reputation, to protect investors who rely on their word, and to disrupt fraudulent activities by their clients.⁶³ The auditor as a gatekeeper certifies a company's financial statements.

Regulation of the audit profession in Jordan is relatively recent. Until 1961, audit practicing was unregulated and practitioners were not required to satisfy any levels of

⁶² JSC dedicates eight staff only to follow in the disclosure requirements.

⁶³ See Anup Agrawal & Sahiba Chadha, Corporate Governance and Accounting Scandals, 48 J. Law & Econ. 371 (2005).

academic knowledge or work experience.⁶⁴ Low-qualified individuals were licensed as auditors.⁶⁵ Now, the Law of the Audit Profession of 2003 regulates auditing in Jordan. The Law of the Audit Profession of 2003 established the Auditing Profession Council to control the profession of auditing in Jordan.⁶⁶ The Auditing Profession Council is not self-regulated association composed of representatives of the audit profession, but rather it is government-dominated.⁶⁷ The Auditing Profession Council has no staff to enforce higher auditing standards.

The number of audit firms and offices has expanded over time. At present, there are about 350 auditing companies operate in Jordan. The Big Four audit firms such as Ernst & Young and Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu and prominent local audit firms such as Saba & Co. dominate the market for companies.

In the past, Jordan encouraged but did not mandate international accounting and auditing standards for companies.⁶⁸ However, in 2002, any company is required by law to prepare and disclose financial and operating data in accordance with internationally recognized accounting and auditing standards.⁶⁹ The auditor is required to issue a report

⁶⁴ See Modar Ali Abdullatif, *The Role of Auditing in Jordan: An Empirical Study of Responsibilities and Expectations* 85 (2003) (unpublished Ph.D dissertation, University of Manchester) (on file with author).

⁶⁵ Individuals possessing only intermediate school certificates and few years of experience were allowed to practice auditing. *Id.* 86.

⁶⁶ In order to be licensed as auditor, he must possess at least a first university degree in accounting or another subject and experience. All applicants for a license must sit for an audit examination. See Provisional Law of the Audit Profession No. 73 of 2003, Official Gazette No. 4606, art. 22 (June 16, 2003).

⁶⁷ The Auditing Profession Council consists of twelve members who include: representatives from the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Industry and Trade, and the General Director of the Income Tax Department. *Id.* art. 4.

⁶⁸ See Victoria Beard & Ziad Al-Rai, *Collection and Transmission of Accounting Information across Cultural Borders: The Case of US MNEs in Jordan*, 34:1 *J. Int'l Accounting* 133, 139, 144 (1999).

⁶⁹ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 184.a. Internationally recognized accounting and auditing rules are rules issued by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB). U.S. Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) are rules, which were developed by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB), are typically more detailed and prescriptive than other countries. U.S. GAAP is a technical accounting term that encompasses the conventions, rules, and procedures necessary to define accepted accounting practices at a particular time.

indicating whether he obtained all the necessary information and whether the company in question complies with international accounting and auditing standards.⁷⁰ The auditor can issue an approval, qualified opinion, or rejection.

One could argue that required disclosure of financial records under the Companies Law of 1997 is not significantly helpful in assisting enforcement of fiduciary duties because management is unlikely to disclose information indicating the breach of such a duty, even if it is required to do so. Devices designed to ensure proper disclosure include the required involvement of independent auditors mitigate this concern. Financial results are required by law to be audited by an independent auditor.⁷¹

The general assembly appoints the auditor upon nomination by the audit committee.⁷² The audit committee consists of three non-executive directors whose responsibilities include nominating an auditor, ensure that all the information needed by the auditor is provided, and review the action plan as presented by the auditor. The requirement that companies have an audit committee responsible for monitoring both the financial reporting process and the audit of the companies' accounts is one of the most important guarantees of auditors' independence. However, there are several drawbacks that affect the efficiency of the audit committee. Audit Committee members are not required to be independent. They are only required to be non-executive directors. Moreover, the Companies Law of 1997 neither requires that the audit committee members have basic financial understanding nor that any member be a financial expert.

IASB attempts to close the gap between its rules and those of America's standard-setter, FASB. See A question of measurement; Accounting standards, *The Economist* (Oct. 23, 2004).

⁷⁰ *Id.* art. 195.

⁷¹ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 142.

⁷² Since 1997, companies have been required to set up an audit committee. *Id.* art. 171.

According to the Companies Law of 1997, the audit committee shall be responsible for the selection of the auditor to be appointed by the shareholders general assembly. Thus, the final decision on the appointment of the auditor lies in the shareholders general assembly. However, in practice, the board of directors of Jordanian companies appoints the auditor and sets his compensation. This is in clear contradiction with the principle of independence of the auditors from the management.

To reinforce auditors' independence and reduce conflict of interest, the Companies Law of 1997 forbids auditing firms to perform any audit service if certain officers of the issuer were employed by that audit firm.⁷³ Moreover, the Law of the Audit Profession of 2003 imposes an obligation on auditors to report to all critical accounting policies, alternative treatments of financial information and other material written communication with the management.⁷⁴ However, the Law of the Audit Profession of 2003 does not specify whether auditors can perform non audit services.

Fees received during the client's reporting period are to be disclosed in the annual financial report. It should be highlighted, however, that it is unclear whether audit fees should not be based on any form of contingency or influenced by the provision of additional services to the audited entity. There is lack of a comprehensive regulation on important issues such as public oversight, disciplinary systems and ethical codes. With regard to the dismissal and resignation of auditors, the Companies Law of 1997 does not require that the auditor can only be dismissed on proper grounds.

The Companies Law of 1997 regulates auditor's civil liability in order to ensure the compensation for the auditor's wrongful acts. Liability can arise out of irregular

⁷³ *Id.* art. 197.

⁷⁴ See Provisional Law of the Audit Profession No. 73 of 2003, *supra* note 66, art. 35.

certification of financial statements and non-disclosure of fraud.⁷⁵ Not only the auditor is liable to the audited entity, but he is also liable to shareholders and third parties.⁷⁶

The language of the Companies Law of 1997 suggests auditor's unlimited liability. Thus, an auditor can be sued for mere negligence. However, the liability of an auditor should be limited by raising the standard of culpability. For example, an auditor should be held liable if he acted with the intent to deceive or committed grossly negligent conduct. Alternatively, an auditor's responsibility could be limited in proportion to his fault. Proportional liability allocates fairly the liability between the audited company's management and the auditor thus discouraging inflated claims and encouraging everyone to be aware of his responsibilities. Under Jordan law, there seem to be no provisions regarding insurance cover to satisfy auditor's liability.⁷⁷

A time limit is set for suing an auditor in civil case. The length of the limitation period is three years starting on the date the company's general assembly meeting where the auditor's report is read.⁷⁸ The purpose of such a provision is to require diligent prosecution of claims, thus providing predictability and finality. Regretfully, liability of auditors (civil, criminal and administrative) has not been tested in courts.

⁷⁵ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 168 & 200.

⁷⁶ *Id.* 201.

⁷⁷ Insurance would cover honest mistakes of judgment, but not intentional misbehavior. Persons would not want to occupy auditor positions unless they were protected in situations where they had simply committed errors of judgment. With insurance, moreover, a corporation does not have to bear the entire cost of auditor negligence, because the risk of misfeasance is spread among all corporations as a cost of doing business.

⁷⁸ See Companies Law No. 22 of 1997, Official Gazette No. 4202 (May 15, 1997), *supra* note 12, art. 201.

Conclusions

Issues of corporate governance are now found on the agenda in Jordan and changes may be in the offing. Indeed, the very term “corporate governance” has entered the Jordanian corporate lexicon. Corporate governance is also frequently the subject of articles in the popular press in Jordan.

Although the Companies Law of 1997 incorporates important measures, there are weaknesses in the corporate governance system in areas such as independent directors, compensation, and auditing rules. Jordan should implement a model corporate governance system for its capital market. The model corporate governance system can be drawn from best practices from around the world but adapted to the local Jordanian market. In the alternative, Jordan could enact Code of Corporate Governance that pulls many existing corporate governance standards together in one place.

Shareholders are permitted to do two things: voting and suing. They also have a third action that they can take: selling their shares. However, shareholders only get to vote on a few fundamental corporate changes. Shareholders get to elect directors annually, but management almost always selects the nominees. In addition, directors control the agenda containing the matters on which shareholders get to vote.

The well-known legal remedies that protect shareholders from opportunism by management or by controlling blocks of shareholders are non-existent in Jordan. Absent in the Companies Law of 1997 is preemptive rights for shareholders. This absence significantly impairs the rights of minority shareholders by leaving them without economic protection and active participation in the business. Absent in the Companies Law of 1997 is also derivative suits to minority shareholders. The Companies Law should be changed to permit a derivative suit to be brought by a shareholder who owns five

percent of the stock, a threshold level that is low and not too restrictive. The five percent ownership requirement is so generous it would make the law largely useful.

The role of institutional investors in Jordan will evolve in coming years. Institutional investors in Jordan could issue their own corporate governance guidelines, and will vote the stock they hold in accordance with the governance principles set forth in those guidelines. Institutional investors can be expected actively to monitor company performance because of the expertise they possess. Thus, institutional investors could engage company management in dialogue regarding significant governance issues.

The Jordanian disclosure regime, if it desires to become effective, must pay regard to the issue of timing. Timely disclosure operates to eliminate company surprises. Jordan must replace the rules for related party transactions such as transaction between directors, general manager, and the company. The definition of “related party transaction” must be clearly defined. Family members of directors should not be excluded from prohibition of related party transaction.

The Companies Law of 1997 establishes the skeleton of the structure by which companies are governed. The law identifies the board with which corporate power ultimately resides. The Companies Law identifies one additional group - stakeholders – but does not specify their role in governance. In the Companies Law, the role of stakeholders comes nowhere close to that prescribed for directors and shareholders. Officers are, in fact, barely mentioned. The companies Law leaves officers’ identity, qualifications, method of selection, and removal entirely to board resolutions and the company’s bylaws. Other stakeholder groups such as creditors, suppliers, the public, or

others whom the corporation's business may impact, have no governance role under the law.

Stakeholders depend upon the corporation for their welfare. Moreover, stakeholders are affected by the manner in which management conducts the corporation's affairs. Therefore, the Companies Law should be amended to give directors permission to consider the interests of groups other than shareholders when making business decisions.

The Companies Law does not provide a test to ensure that the auditor is truly independent from the influence of management. The appointment of the auditor should be independent from those who prepare the financial statements of the audited entity. The auditor should be appointed by the general meeting of shareholders. To improve auditor's independence from executive directors, Jordan must comprehensive regulation of such important issues as public oversight, disciplinary systems and ethical codes for auditors. All auditors should be subject to quality assurance systems.

The Companies Law should omit the requirement that substantial shareholders are entitled to seats on the board of directors. The likely result of this requirement is boards of directors manned by unqualified individuals and the inability of a company to achieve an independent board. In addition, Jordan law must detail duties, responsibilities, and functions of board of directors. A training program for board members must be implemented to give an understanding of their roles and duties. As corporate governance standards are improved and directors are held to higher standards, it is important that the Companies Law incorporates a business judgment rule and provides guidance concerning when reliance on information and advice would be considered to be reasonable.

There are many agencies responsible directly or indirectly for the regulation of corporate governance in Jordan. The Companies Law is within the domain of the Ministry of Industry and Trade while the Securities Law is within the domain of the Jordanian Ministry of Finance. Amman Stock Exchange requires that the companies whose stock is traded on the exchange comply with certain listing requirements, many of which directly address issues of corporate governance. The accounting rulemaking bodies in Jordan also focus on implementing corporate governance standards. Bureaucratic turf issues like these may complicate corporate governance reform efforts in Jordan.

Jordan should seek to promote a culture of compliance, transparency and accountability without restraining business initiative. Jordan must also have the will and the proper means to enforce existing laws and regulations, otherwise there is little reason to adopt more, even arguably better, corporate governance regulations. Jordan must demonstrate that it will prosecute board members in egregious cases. Moreover, Jordanian companies need to know that effective corporate governance is an important element of a successful business and can be an invaluable asset for companies seeking external financing. There must be change in mindset.